

Synthesis of recyclable polymeric chelator containing hydroxy pyridinone ligands for actinides

Nirmal Koshti*, Bharat Parab and Shubhangi Naik

Galaxy Research Centre, Galaxy Surfactants Ltd., C-49/2, TLC Ind'l Area, Pawne, Navi Mumbai-400 703, India

E-mail : Nirmal.Koshti@galaxysurfactants.com

Manuscript received 20 August 2003, revised 9 March 2004, accepted 23 August 2004

Facile synthesis of waters-soluble poly(*N,N*-diethyl acrylamide) bound hydroxy pyridinone (HOPO) is reported. The polymeric chelator has been shown to bind a representative actinide, Th^{IV}, quantitatively at pH 3.0. Its utility in extraction of metal ion from its aqueous solution is demonstrated. This recyclable polymeric chelator has potential use in nuclear waste remediation since it contains plutonophile HOPO ligands.

Actinide ions such as plutonium and americium have higher co-ordination number (eight or more) and somewhat flexible ligand geometry (octadentate, square anti-prism or dodecahedral) compared to most other metal ions. Since the plutonium(IV) ion is a hard Lewis acid, the preferred ligands that have been incorporated into the synthetic chelators have been catecholates, hydroxypyridinones and hydroxamates¹. Raymond and coworkers have developed a number of cyclic and acyclic chelators for the binding of plutonium, some of which are potentially useful for *in vivo* biodecorporation of this metal ion². Williams *et al.*¹ have compared around forty chelating ligands of differing denticity and basicity for recovery of Pu from process waste streams. One of the three potential cost effective plutonophiles that was identified by them is Raymond's 3-hydroxy-2-pyridinone (HOPO) analogue of the siderophore, Desferrioxamine B. In addition to monomeric chelators, water-soluble polymeric hydroxamates from polyethyleneimine and polyallylamine for chelation of actinides have been reported^{3,4}. In this approach, metal-polymeric ligand complexes are separated by membrane-filtration. However, these water-soluble polymeric chelators cannot be recycled.

Results and discussion

In this paper, we report a water-soluble polymeric chelator that binds Th^{IV} and that can be recycled. This has been achieved by exploiting the thermo-sensitivity of aqueous solution of poly(*N,N*-diethyl acrylamide) (PDEA)⁵. PDEA has lower critical solution temperature (LCST) of 33°C. It undergoes thermally induced reversible phase transition. Below the LCST, the polymer molecules exist in solution as extended coils, surrounded by water molecules. This shell of hydration causes a decrease in entropy of the

system. Thus, the free energy of solution is lowered by the formation of hydrogen bonds but is raised by loss of entropy. At temperatures above LCST, the entropy term dominates and the polymer precipitates out of the solution. We have accomplished water-soluble recyclable chelating polymer by anchoring HOPO units onto PDEA using short synthetic sequences depicted in Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1

The copolymer (**1**) was synthesized from *N,N*-diethyl acrylamide and vinyl azalactone (2-vinyl-4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazoline-5-one) (8 : 2) using AIBN as an initiator in *t*-butanol. The IR spectrum of **1** showed a prominent stretch for carbonyl of azalactone at 1814 cm⁻¹ and carbonyl of amide at 1646 cm⁻¹. The molecular weight (M_n) was found to be in the range of 20000 based on the GPC analysis of **2**. Unfortunately, due to broad signals, PMR spectrum was not of any help in ascertaining the mole ratio of monomers in **1** vis-à-vis the feed ratio. However, the relative mole ratio of *N,N*-diethyl acrylamide to vinyl azalactone could be easily determined by reacting azalactone units of **1** with dimethyl amino propyl diamine and finding out the amine value of the resultant product. Using this method the actual mole ratio of the monomers was found to be quite close to the feed ratio. Next, the HOPO ligand was anchored on the copolymer (**2**) by quaternisation of tertiary amino group with 3-(hydroxy)-1-(*N*-3-chloropropyl acetamido)-2-(1*H*)-pyridinone (**3**). The introduction of ionic centres in the PDEA bound HOPO increased the LCST from 33 to 45°C.

3-(Hydroxy)-1-(*N*-3-chloropropyl acetamido)-2-(1*H*)-pyridinone (**3**) was prepared from 3-(benzyloxy)-1-(carboxy methyl)-2-(1*H*)-pyridinone that was in turn prepared from commercially available 2,3-dihydroxy pyridine following a literature⁶ procedure (Scheme 2). The *N*-carboxy methyl hydroxyl pyridinone was coupled with 3-chloropropylamine in the presence of 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole. Debenzylation of this intermediate was effected by hydrogenolysis to yield chloro terminated hydroxy pyridinone (**3**). All steps described in Schemes 1 and 2 were high yielding and the compounds were completely characterized.

Scheme 2

The copolymer (**4**) (200 mg) was treated with 25 ml of 15 ppm solution of the Th^{IV} (corresponding nitrate was used). After adjusting the pH 3.0, the polymer bound complex was precipitated by heating the aqueous solution above its LCST. The supernatant was then analyzed for residual uncomplexed Th^{IV} by spectrophotometry⁷ using Arsenazo-I and measuring the absorbance of the complex at 579 nm. The spectrophotometric analysis revealed the recovery of

Th^{IV} to be 94%. The polymer bound complex of the metal ion was dissolved in water and treated with excess EDTA. The polymeric chelator was recovered again by heating the aqueous solution and was used for next cycle. In this manner, it was successfully recycled thrice.

Metal-ligand complexation as a function of pH and selectivity of this polymeric chelator in binding transition metal ions as well as actinides is being studied.

In summary, we have demonstrated a facile synthesis of thermally reversible polymeric chelator using commercially available 2,3-dihydroxy pyridine and monomers like *N,N*-diethyl acrylamide and vinyl azalactone. The metal chelation efficiency and the recyclability of this polymeric chelator make it very cost effective.

Experimental

All reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial sources and used without purification unless otherwise stated. Vinyl azalactone was obtained from SNPE Chimie, France. All other chemicals were purchased from Aldrich. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained on a Varian's Mercury Plus 300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Infrared spectra were reported as thin films between NaCl plates or as pressed KBr pellets using Perkin-Elmer's Spectrum 1 FT-IR spectrometer. UV-Visible spectra were obtained using Varian's Cary 50 spectrometer. GPC analysis was performed using Varian's HPLC, ProStar 240 equipped with Gilson's 133 refractive index detector.

*Synthesis of poly(N,N-diethyl acrylamide-*c*-vinyl azalactone) (1)* : *N,N*-Diethyl acrylamide (10.0 g, 78.74 mmol) and vinyl azalactone (2.74 g, 19.7 mmol) were dissolved in *t*-butanol at 65°C under nitrogen. A solution of AIBN (240 mg) in *t*-butanol was added to the above solution. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 h at 80–85°C. The concentrated reaction mixture obtained after removal of *t*-butanol on a rotary evaporator was slowly added to petroleum ether (500 ml) under stirring. The precipitate was filtered and dried under vacuum to yield the copolymer as white solid (10.94 g, 85.74%). IR (KBr) 1814, 1729, 1646 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) showed broad signals in the region between δ 1.0 to 3.5. The vinylic protons were totally absent.

*Synthesis of poly(N,N-diethyl acrylamide-*c*-vinyl azalactone) bound dimethyl amino propyl diamine (2)* : A mixture of poly(*N,N*-diethyl acrylamide-*c*-vinyl azalactone) (5.0 g, 7.73 mmol of VAL units) and dimethyl amino propyl diamine (1.57 g, 15.46 mmol) in *t*-butanol (50 ml) was stirred at 50°C for 10 h. The product obtained after removal of *t*-butanol was further purified by dissolving it in water

and reprecipitating by heating the aqueous solution at 50°C. Drying of this precipitate yielded the amino terminated copolymer as white solid (3.9 g, 67.38%) that had amine value of 68.9 as against expected 74.96. IR (KBr) 3435 (broad), 2976, 1630 (broad) cm^{-1} . The stretching for carbonyl of azalactone ring was absent. ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_3OD) showed broad signals at δ 1.1, 2.1 and 3.25. Size exclusion chromatography of 0.1% aqueous solution of the polymer on column (Ultrasphere 2000, Waters, hydroxylated polymethacrylate gel) using 100% water as mobile phase and refractive index detection gave M_n of 20000.

Synthesis of 3-(hydroxy)-1-(3-chloropropyl acetamido)-2-(1H)-pyridinone (3) It was synthesized by the following two step procedure

Step 1 A mixture of 3-(benzyloxy)-1-(carboxy methyl)-2-(1H)-pyridinone (1.5 g, 5.79 mmol) and 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole (0.94 g, 5.79 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 ml) was stirred at room temperature for half an hour under nitrogen. To this, a solution of 3-chloropropylamine hydrochloride (0.75 g, 5.79 mmol) and triethylamine (1.76 g, 17.42 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 ml) was added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12 h. The reaction mass was then washed with 10% HCl followed by saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water (10 ml each). Drying (anhydrous sodium sulphate) and removal of dichloromethane yielded the coupled product as white product (1.47 g, 75.82%) m.p. 151–153°C (Found: C, 60.82; H, 5.32. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 60.93, H, 5.68%); IR (KBr) 3256, 1676, 1653 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 1.99 (2H, q, J 6.59 Hz), 3.37 (2H, t, J 6.59 Hz), 3.62 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 4.64 (2H, s), 5.10 (2H, s), 6.27 (1H, t, J 7.33 Hz), 6.98 (1H, d, J^1 7.5 Hz, J^2 1.65 Hz), 7.16 (1H, d, J^1 6.78 Hz, J^2 1.65 Hz), 7.27–7.47 (5H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 31.95, 37.15, 42.36, 54.07, 70.98, 106.10, 116.22, 127.48, 128.29, 128.74, 129.53, 135.54, 148.85, 158.52, 167.45.

Step 2: A solution of 3-(benzyloxy)-1-(3-chloropropyl acetamido)-2-(1H)-pyridinone (1.2 g, 3.62 mmol) in methanol (50 ml), acetic acid (3.0 ml) and 5% Pd/C (500 mg) was stirred under hydrogen atmosphere for 12 h at room temperature. Removal of the catalyst by filtration and subsequent removal of solvent yielded debenzylated product as white solid (0.73 g, 82.66%) m.p. 191–192°C (Found: C, 48.85, H, 5.09. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 49.08, H,

5.32%); IR (KBr) 3293, 3226, 1680, 1651 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 1.98 (2H, q, J 6.59 Hz), 3.37 (2H, t, J 6.59 Hz), 3.62 (2H, t, J 6.4 Hz), 4.63 (2H, s), 6.23 (1H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 6.83 (1H, d, J^1 7.33 Hz, J^2 1.46 Hz), 7.05 (1H, d, J^1 6.96 Hz, J^2 1.46 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 32.12, 36.06, 42.80, 51.32, 104.56, 114.80, 129.29, 146.39, 157.71, 166.65.

Synthesis of poly(*N,N*-diethyl acrylamide-*c*-vinyl azalactone) bound 3-(hydroxy)-1-(3-chloropropyl acetamido)-2-(1H)-pyridinone (4). A solution of poly(*N,N*-diethyl acrylamide) bound dimethyl amino propyl diamine (1.5 g, 23 mmol of vinyl azalactone) and 3-hydroxy-1-(*N*-3-chloropropyl acetamido)-2-(1H)-pyridinone (0.65 g, 26.58 mmol) in *t*-butanol was stirred under nitrogen pressure for 40 h at 85–90°C. The progress of this reaction was monitored by estimating the chloride ion content that was found to be 4.3%. The solvent was removed using a rotary evaporator and residue was dissolved in water. The polymer bound chelator was then precipitated from its aqueous solution by heating the mass above 50°C. This process was repeated twice and the precipitate on drying yielded 1.4 g (65.2%) quaternary polymeric chelator as white solid. IR (KBr) 3467 (broad), 2976 (broad), 2936, 1630 (broad) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, D_2O) showed broad signals in the region between δ 1.1 and 3.25. Olefinic protons of pyridinone ring were observed at δ 6.2, 6.8 and 7.1.

References

- 1 N C Boyle, G P Nicholson, T J Piper, D M Taylor, G Williams and D R Williams, *Appl Radiat Isot*, 1997, **48**, 183
- 2 (a) L C Uhlir, P W Durbin and K N Raymond, *J Med Chem*, 1993, **36**, 504, (b) J Xu, B Kullgren, P W Durbin and K N Raymond, *J Med Chem*, 1995, **38**, 2606
- 3 N M Koshti, A S Gopalan, H K Jacobs and P C Stark, *International Journal of Environmentally Conscious Design and Manufacturing*, 1995, **4**, 19
- 4 N M Koshti, A S Gopalan, H K Jacobs, P C Stark and W Bisset, *Reactive & Functional Polymers*, 2003, **55**, 109
- 5 I Idziac, D Avoco, D Lessard, D Gravel and X X Zhu, *Macromolecules*, 1999, **32**, 1260
- 6 M Streater, P D Taylor, R C Hider and J Porter, *J Med Chem*, 1990, **33**, 1749
- 7 "Spectrophotometric Determination of Elements", ed Z Marzenko, Ellis Harwood Ltd, Chichester, 1976. Chap 58, pp 578-580